

DEFORMATION MICROMECHANICS IN HIGH VOLUME FRACTION ARAMID/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

It is shown that Raman spectroscopy can be used to follow molecular deformation processes in Kevlar 49 aramid fibres. The strain dependence of the 1610 cm^{-1} aramid Raman band is examined in detail and it is shown that there are local variations of fibre strain in deformed fibres. The shift of the same band in a high-volume fraction uniaxially-aligned composite is analysed and it is found that there are significant variations in local fibre strain due to imperfections in the composite. The distributions of axial fibre strain have also been mapped in a 4-harness satin weave Kevlar 49/epoxy composite and it is demonstrated that there are complex distributions of local fibre strain that follow the pattern of the repeat unit of the woven structure.

INTRODUCTION

It has been established that Raman spectroscopy is an excellent method of following the micromechanics of deformation of aramid [1] and other [2,3] high-performance fibres. It has also been demonstrated that Raman spectroscopy can be used to study the deformation micromechanics of aramid fibres in model, single-fibre composites with an epoxy resin matrix [4,5]. By monitoring the peak position of the strain-sensitive 1610 cm^{-1} aramid Raman band it is possible to follow the deformation of the aramid fibres and to define the states of localised stress or strain in a composite matrix. Furthermore, it has been shown that Raman spectroscopy is a powerful analytical technique and can be used to determine the states of localised stress or strain in conventional micromechanical test methods such as fragmentation [6] and single-fibre pull-out [7]. The interfacial shear stress can be calculated from the distribution of strain along the fibre using a simple balance of forces model [4,5].

This presentation is concerned with an extension of the Raman technique to the mapping of fibre strains in high-volume-fraction uniaxial and woven aramid/epoxy composites. Following an investigation of the deformation of single aramid fibres, a detailed analysis is undertaken to determine the dependence of the local strain distributions in high-volume-fraction composites upon the macroscopic level of strain. The distributions of fibre strain in uniaxially-aligned composites and the detailed periodic distributions of strain along the plies in woven composites will be presented.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fibre used in this study was a commercial grade of aramid fibre, Kevlar 49. The fibres had been sized during processing to improve both the handling characteristics and matrix adhesion in composites. They had a diameter of $\sim 12 \mu\text{m}$, a tensile modulus of about 120 GPa, a tensile strength of $\sim 2.6 \text{ GPa}$ and a strain to failure of about 2.2%.

Two composite systems were investigated and both were supplied by CYTEC Aerospace in Wrexham, UK. The composites were cured under vacuum in an autoclave and their details are as follows [8]:

(a) Unidirectional one-ply composite consisting of about 62.5% of Kevlar 49 fibres in Cycom 753, an epoxy resin used extensively in marine applications. The composite was heated up to 100°C at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the temperature was held at 100°C for 60 min.

(b) Four-harness satin weave one-ply composite consisting of about 50% of Kevlar 49 fibres in Cycom 919, a toughened epoxy resin. The composite was heated up to 120°C at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the temperature was held at 120°C for 90 min.

Raman spectra were obtained from the aramid fibres, both in air and within the composites, using the 632.8 nm red line of a 15 mW helium-neon laser focused to a $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$ spot on the surface of the fibre. A highly-sensitive charge-coupled device (CDD) camera was used to collect Raman spectra using an exposure time of 7 seconds. The peak position of the strain sensitive 1610 cm^{-1} Raman band [1] was used to map the fibre strains in the composites at various levels of applied strain.

SINGLE FIBRE DEFORMATION

Figure 1. Strain-induced shift of the 1610 cm^{-1} Raman band for a single filament of Kevlar 49.

The effect of deformation on the Raman spectrum for a single filament of Kevlar 49 is shown in Figure 1. The spectrum shows the region 1560 cm^{-1} to 1670 cm^{-1} and it can be seen that the two main Raman bands at 1610 cm^{-1} and 1645 cm^{-1} shift significantly to lower wavenumber on the application of only 1% strain.

Figure 2. Shift in the position of the 1610 cm^{-1} Raman band for 5 nominally-identical Kevlar 49 fibres subjected to a tensile strain.

This behaviour is shown more clearly in Figure 2 where the peak positions of five nominally-identical Kevlar 49 fibres are plotted as a function of fibre strain. It can be seen that there is an approximately linear shift in peak position with increasing strain and that the behaviour is very reproducible. The rate of band shift per unit strain $d\Delta\nu/de = S$ for the Kevlar 49 fibres in Figure 2 is $-4.83 \pm 0.17\text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain and the correlation coefficient is 0.9988.

Rallis [8] has undertaken a detailed study of the statistics of the stress-induced band shifts in Kevlar 49 fibres. He took 80 measurements of the band peak position for a fibre strained to about 0.25% both at the same position on the fibre and also randomly over a 20 mm region, using a spot size of the order of $2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in both cases. It was found that when the laser beam was focused on the same area of the fibre the standard deviation of the band peak position was very narrow (S.D. = 0.033 cm^{-1}) whereas if the measurements are taken randomly over a 20 mm region the distribution of peak positions was broader (S.D. = 0.061 cm^{-1}). This implies that there are imperfections in the fibres, such as a local variation of fibre diameter, although in both cases the distributions of peak position were relatively narrow.

Following the detailed analysis of the statistics of the Raman bands positions at a constant strain, Rallis [8] looked at the development of the broadening of the distributions of the Raman band peak positions (and hence local fibre strain) of the 1610 cm^{-1} Kevlar 49 Raman band during deformation. Figure 3 shows the shift and broadening of the distributions of local fibre strain for 80 measurements taken at random over a 20 mm region of the fibre. It can be seen that there is a significant increase in the standard deviation (S.D.) of the strain upon deformation up to 1.55% strain that reflects a real spread in the local strain levels in the fibres, over and above any

apparent spread due to random error in the measurements [8]. It is important to consider the origin of this behaviour. It is clearly a result of inhomogeneity in the deformation of the fibres, perhaps due to local variations in fibre structure and/or geometry.

Figure 3. Histograms showing the local fibre strains determined from the 1610 cm^{-1} Raman band peak positions for a Kevlar 49 fibre subjected to increasing levels of strain for 80 measurements obtained at random over a 20 mm region. (a) Fibre strain of 0.25%, (b) Fibre strain of 0.66%, (c) Fibre strain of 1.07%, (d) Fibre strain of 1.55%.

UNIAXIAL COMPOSITE

A series of measurements have been undertaken of the local strains in the Kevlar 49 uniaxial composite subjected to axial deformation. In this case 200 measurements were obtained randomly at four different composite strain levels, e_c , determined using a resistance strain gauge attached to the specimen. The results are presented in the form of histograms in Figure 4

Figure 4. Histograms showing the local fibre strains determined from the 1610 cm^{-1} Raman band peak positions for a uniaxial Kevlar 49/epoxy composite subjected to increasing levels of strain for 200 measurements obtained at random over the composite surface.

(a) Composite strain of 0%, (b) strain of 0.2%, (c) strain of 0.4%, (d) strain of 0.6%.

It can be seen that axial stressing of the composite leads to tensile deformation of the fibres in the composite. Moreover the average strain in the fibres is similar to value of the composite strain, e_c , given by the strain gauge. What is most interesting, however, is that there is significant spread in the distribution of fibre strain that increases with increasing composite strain. This is significantly higher than the spread in the distribution of fibre strain that develops during the deformation of single fibres (Figure 3) and shows clearly that in the high-volume fraction composite there is a large local variation of fibre strain. This is most likely to be due to factors such as variations in local fibre orientation, packing density etc.

WOVEN COMPOSITES

An optical micrograph of the 4-harness satin weave fabric used in the woven composite is shown in Figure 5. The point-to-point variation of local fibre deformation was determined for the woven composite using strain-induced Raman band shifts from the fibres in the composites subjected to axial deformation. This was done by first of all taking a series of Raman spectra at 50 μm intervals along the centre of a tow of fibres lying in the horizontal direction in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Optical micrograph of the 4-harness satin weave Kevlar 49 fabric used in the woven composite

Figure 6. Variation of fibre strain with distance along the centre of the repeat pattern of interlaced threads (weft face) at two levels of composite strain derived from stress-induced Raman band shifts.

Figure 6 shows the derived variation of fibre strain along the horizontal fibres in Figure 5. At a composite strain of 0% (i.e. undeformed) the fibres are virtually unstrained indicating that in this composite the thermal stresses are very low. A sketch of the weave pattern is also given in the Figure and it can be seen that the distribution of fibre strain at a composite strain of 1% follows that pattern of the weave very closely. It can be seen that where the horizontal fibres are at the surface the axial fibre strain is of the order of 1% although it is highest where the fibres emerge from under the crossing fibres and is a minimum in the centre of this region. Values of strain are also given in Figure 6 for the crossing fibres even though they are perpendicular to the straining direction and the direction of polarisation of the laser beam. The Raman signal from such fibres is very weak and so the data are rather scattered. Nevertheless, it shows that the crossing fibres are subjected to an axial strain of between 0.2% and 0.7% and there is also a definite repeating pattern in the distribution of fibre strain in the crossing fibres.

Figure 7. Variation of fibre strain with distance along the centre of the repeat pattern of interlaced threads (warp face) at two levels of composite strain derived from stress-induced Raman band shifts.

The point-to-point variation of fibre strain was also determined in Figure 7 for the horizontal fibres on the opposite warp face of the woven composite subjected to axial deformation in the horizontal direction. (This is equivalent of turning the micrograph in Figure 5 though 90°). When there is no applied stress the fibres are virtually undeformed indicating the lack of thermal residual stresses in the fibres. It can again be seen that a complex repeating pattern emerges when the composite is deformed. In this case 3/4 of the fibres appear on the surface and again they are subject to a variable strain of the order of 1% at $e_c=1\%$. The strain is high where the fibres emerge from underneath the crossing plies. It then decreases but peaks in the centre of this region. It can be seen that the transverse fibres are less stressed with a tensile strain of the order of 0.3-0.5%.

CONCLUSIONS

It is clear that Raman spectroscopy is a powerful technique to follow deformation processes in aramid fibres and composites. There are small but measurable local variations of fibre strain in Kevlar 49 fibres deformed in air due probably to minor imperfections in the fibres. It has been shown that there are larger variations of the strain in individual fibres in a deformed high volume fraction uniaxially-aligned Kevlar 49/epoxy composite due to local imperfections in the composite structure. One of the most exciting findings has been that it is possible to map of the point-to-point variation of fibre strain in the woven composite. It has been found that the patterns of fibre strain follow closely the repeat units of the woven structure. This shows that the technique has considerable potential in being able to map the local fibre deformation in such complex structures and offers the possibility of being able to analyse the deformation micromechanics in such systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by a Research Grant from the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council. One of the authors (R.J.Y.) is grateful to the Royal Society for support in the form of the Wolfson Research Professorship in Materials Science and another (N.R.) would like to thank the Bodossakis Foundation and the Alexander S. Onassis Public Benefit Foundation for support in the form of scholarships.

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